

The trawler as a catch platform: an exploration of design for modularity

Jesper van der Meij^{1,*}, Lars Erik Nygård¹, Ola Jon Mork¹, and Karl Henning Halse¹

¹ Norwegian University of Science and Technology, Ålesund, Norway

Abstract. Oceangoing bottom trawlers are the largest fishing vessels sailing in Norwegian waters. All oceangoing trawlers have some form of onboard factory that processes the catch into a marketable product. The vessel, and especially the factory, is normally designed for a specific fishing mission. The ship is built around a factory that is delivered as a package, which means there is very limited customization possible in the operational phase. With ever changing framework conditions in the fishing sector, trawler owners benefit from increased resource flexibility: being able to decide what species to fish and what product to create. In this work, an alternative to the current practice is presented: to employ a modular design on the trawler, where system components can be exchanged based on mission demand. The term catch platform is introduced to change thinking of the trawler from a fishing vessel to a flexible operation platform. A functional description of the systems on the trawler is given, examining which systems could benefit most from being made modular. Key considerations for designing the trawler as a catch platform are presented. Finally, an example of a combined whitefish and shrimp trawler is used to further outline the idea. It is concluded that there are various challenges to be solved before modular design in trawlers becomes common practice. Nevertheless, opening the discussion of change on this vessel type is required to secure the continued sustainable exploitation of fish stocks.

Key words: *Modular design, Oceangoing trawlers, Operation platform*

1. Introduction

Oceangoing bottom trawlers are the largest fishing vessels sailing in Norwegian waters. In a broad sense, a trawler operates by dragging a net through the water, thereby capturing the marine life it encounters (a sketch can be seen in Figure 2.). All oceangoing trawlers have in addition some form of onboard factory that processes the catch into a marketable product.

When designing a ship, the first step is to detail the purpose of the design. This is called the mission statement [1]. For the trawler, we introduce the term "fishing mission": the description of what species the ship will fish on, in what location and at what time. This is used together with the product strategy, which outlines what products to produce on board. Based on these considerations and the preferences of the shipowner, requirements to the design of the ship and systems on board are set.

The most important species for the oceangoing trawlers in Norway are whitefish: cod, saithe, and haddock. There is also fishing on other bottom species such as Greenland halibut. Additionally, most vessels target shrimp some part of the year to maintain fishing activity when whitefish quota runs out. [2] The catch occurs in large parts in the Norwegian, Greenland, and Barents Seas – that is, mainly in the Norwegian EEZ. The catch is processed and frozen on board, before delivery to facilities along the Norwegian coast. There are two main options for the onboard processing of whitefish. By far the most common is to produce headed and gutted (HG) fish, frozen in blocks. These are further processed on land, either in Norway or abroad. The other option is making fillets on board, which are shipped for either wholesale or retail when delivered on land. Shrimp may be rinsed and frozen in blocks, or boiled before freezing. The latter is uncommon on the combined whitefish and shrimp trawlers due to the space and energy required for the boiler. In all cases, a fishing trip where catch is frozen may take from four to six weeks depending on conditions. Additionally, most vessels have capacity for storing fresh fish, which is done in a part of the season when prices are high. In this case, a fishing trip will only last a few days.

*Correspondence to: jesper.van.der.meij@ntnu.no

As opposed to some other natural resources, fish is a highly varying resource. Fishers have always had to adapt to changing framework conditions and the availability of fish stocks [3, 4], leading to uncertainty when designing the ship [5]. In order to account for this uncertainty, the design of the ship and its components must be adapted to the current fishing mission. Examples of components that stand out as different for each individual fishing mission are the trawl gear and factory components.

Currently, however, the ship and factory are designed and delivered as a package according to engineering-to-order practices. This leads to a two-part challenge: Firstly, predictions of future mission demand must be made early in the design phase, typically years ahead of delivery. As these predictions are uncertain, many 'safety factors' are implemented, resulting in a robust design that is generally over-dimensioned. Secondly, as the ship is closed around the factory, there is very limited customisation possible in the operational phase. This means a shipowner is 'stuck' with the design even when framework conditions change. The high cost of intensive modifications means it often makes more sense to sell the ship than to adapt the design to the new conditions. This results in trawlers in the Norwegian fleet having a relatively short renewal time, something that is seen as both positive and negative: on the one hand there is greater possibility for innovation on board, but on the other hand the continuous investment costs are large and there is no time for the company to build a buffer.

Next to adapting to framework conditions, increased resource flexibility allows for capitalising on (seasonal) variations in the price of products. For example, there is potential for better utilisation of the residual raw material (RRM) in the Norwegian whitefish industry [6]. Better utilisation of the RRM also contributes to the global trend in making seafood more sustainable, something that is being increasingly recognised by the customer. The RRM is rich in proteins, lipids, and other nutrients that can be used to produce ingredients for both human consumption and for animal feed. For the shipowner, this could increase the value created on board by 3–10%, however currently – in a factory where components cannot be switched out in operation – the additional space and crew requirement was found to lead to a decrease in all scenarios [7].

An alternative to the current practice is to employ a modular design on the trawler, where system components can be exchanged based on mission demand in the operation phase. This design for modularity has in limited cases been successfully applied to other vessel types. More specifically, the deck equipment of coastal fishing vessels employs a sort of modularity, where a trawl winch can be switched out for a net drum when changing fishing method. However, there are no examples of this for systems inside the oceangoing trawler, such as the factory or energy system. In general, modular design for the operational phase of ships has not been institutionalised and a standard design methodology does not exist [8].

The main goal of the present study is thus to explore the use of modular design on the oceangoing trawler vessel type. We aim to change the way of thinking of the trawler: from a fishing vessel to a flexible "catch platform", that allows the shipowner to be more resilient to external change.

In Section 2., we present the current state of modular ship design through examples from other ship types. This leads into the considerations and steps required when designing a modular ship. In Section 3., we introduce the trawler as a catch platform by going through these steps. In Section 4. we then give a more concrete example of the combined whitefish and shrimp trawler, commenting on the design changes required to allow for exchanging modules. Finally in Section 5. we discuss the results, further work, and give a broader outlook to the new generation of oceangoing trawlers.

2. Ship Design for Modularity

In ship design, the Design for Modularity strategy refers to "subdividing the ship into well-defined parts and components that can later be recombined according to given rules and procedures" [9]. This requires the ship to be designed as a product with a modular architecture, where the functions and physical components are decoupled from each other. Ulrich [10] defines three types of product architecture based on the interfaces between components:

- Slot architecture is where each of the interfaces between components is of a different type, so components cannot be directly interchanged.
- Bus architecture contains a common bus to which the other components connect via the same type of interface.

Figure 1. Component swapping modularity in the TES [13].

- Sectional architecture finally defines all interfaces to be of the same type and there is no common component to which the other components attach.

Salvador et al. [11] expands on this by introducing component swapping architecture, where there is a common component that the other components connect, but the interfaces are of a type specific to the module.

Modularity can be applied at various stages of a ship's lifecycle. In the design phase, modularity enables standardisation through product platform strategies. Designers can reuse earlier designs by recombining modules in a different way, making the design process more efficient and supporting innovation. During the production phase, modularity can make the supply chain more effective and speed up the building process by enabling for early outfitting and procurement packing [9]. Especially relevant for the current work, however, is modularity in the operation phase. Enabling for the exchange of components means the ship can be used as an operation platform: a common basis for multiple configurations of a flexible product [12]. This offers flexible mission selection, which means the vessel can adapt to changing conditions such as regulation, technology, and markets. It also means modernisation and retrofit is easier and module investment decisions can be delayed until the module is needed.

Doerry [8] refers to a vessel that uses a flexible design to adapt to changing requirements as a "Modular Adaptable Ship" (MAS). Through examples of MAS technology and processes, it is highlighted that these have only been incorporated into ship designs in an unstructured manner. The article concludes that estimating costs and valuing modularity should be emphasized first.

Probably the most straightforward example of a vessel type that benefits from flexible mission selection is the naval vessel. The US Navy's Test and Evaluation Ship (TES), Figure 1., is an example of the use of component swapping modularity, in this case for testing new equipment. Predefined locations and interfaces for each type of equipment allows for rapid changeout. The ship was sized such that the design of the platform could be used unchanged as long as possible [13].

Another concrete example from the Navy is the Littoral Combat Ship, where different mission modules can be plugged into a standard interface (bus architecture) to adapt to a changing mission. While the design

Figure 2. Sketch of a trawler and the placement of systems on board.

shows the potential of modular systems, it also came with a slew of issues. The Navy's haste to deliver the ships led to technical failures and incomplete modular systems, while the complexity of the systems meant the crew was unable to maintain them by themselves. This example highlights the need for thorough testing and integration of modular systems in future projects [14].

Another ship type where MAS has been applied is offshore vessels. For example, a case study on a vessel with four distinct missions and a number of key capabilities is presented by Choi et al. [12]. They developed an optimisation model for designing an operation platform, based on examining interfaces that affect the flexibility of the modules.

Pfeifer et al. [15] presents a study on electric ferries, noting that the high degree of dependency between components means that modularisation approaches can hardly be found in the maritime industry.

More similar to the topic presented in the current work is the use of modular thinking in coastal fishing vessels, where a trawl winch might be exchanged for a net drum when switching from pelagic trawling to purse seine fishing. While of very limited impact to the overall design of the vessel, this example furthermore shows that the practical benefits of being able to exchange components are recognised.

3. The trawler as a catch platform

We introduce the term "catch platform" to refer to the trawler that is designed with modular systems. In that case, we should think of the trawler no longer as a fishing vessel, but rather an operation platform used to catch and process marine life. This implies obtaining the mission flexibility that is sought after: the shipowner can decide what species to fish, in which location and at which time (fishing mission) and what products to create on board (product strategy) based on the modules placed on the vessel. Some key considerations for designing the trawler as a catch platform are presented in this section.

3.1. System distribution

The first step is to distribute the ship into several interconnected systems that each have their own individual function. Figure 2. shows a representation of how the systems of a trawler can be spatially distributed. Later, the systems may be broken down further into sub-systems and components in a higher level of detail. We comment on each system's potential for modularity. This assessment is based on the foreseen benefits versus the costs of introducing modularity. Here, costs include direct investment costs, but also indirect costs such as adding technological complexity or difficulties with exchanging modules. A quantification of these costs has not been started. Still, the considerations presented here should illustrate the idea of the trawler as a catch platform well.

A Trawl gear: responsible for capturing and retaining the catch, consisting of the net, doors, and wires. In essence, we could see this as already being a modular system. It is not complicated to switch out the net in operation and while most vessels have only one set of doors on board during a fishing trip, it is common to exchange these when the ship is docked. Changing the gear is done when it is in need for repair, or when fishing for different species and a different mesh size is needed.

- B Gear handling: responsible for controlling the trawl gear, consisting of winches, blocks, and cranes. The example from the coastal fishing vessels given in the previous section refers to this system. For the oceangoing trawler, a possible benefit could be gained from facilitating for the addition of a trawl winch or ice trawl equipment. A key consideration here is on the ship's stability and seagoing capabilities when adding weight on the deck.
- C Processing factory: responsible for processing the catch into a marketable product, consisting of the equipment on the factory deck. Here is where the greatest potential for modularisation is foreseen. For example, to change equipment when fishing for a different species, or change packaging sizes when the consumer market becomes attractive. A modular solution could allow for new business cases to arise, perhaps through leasing of processing machines instead of owning them. A modular solution might open up to new markets as well, for example to fish for crab. A component that stands out as being less suitable for modularisation is the freezers, as on one hand most products will be frozen and on the other hand the supply of refrigerant is not straightforward to change.
- D Storage: responsible for keeping the product in a stable state, consisting of the cargo hold. Here we foresee limited potential in modularisation. Generally, the hold should be able to store every kind of product. And given all product is frozen, this limits the variation in storage method and product size. There could however be a benefit to accommodate for portable storage tanks for liquid products in the cargo hold, such as fish oil. It might also be beneficial to be able to subdivide the cargo hold by placing vertical insulated bulkheads such that the space can be used for other functions.
- E Hull: responsible for the structural integrity of the ship, consisting of plating and structural elements. Here we foresee no changes, as it is challenging to facilitate exchanging parts of the hull in operation. An example of the use of a modular hull would be to change out the bulbous bow when sailing at a different draft or speed. However, we do not foresee large enough changes in the fishing mission to defend accommodating for this.
- F Propulsion: responsible for manoeuvring the vessel, consisting of the propeller and drive components. As the propeller is matched to the hull form and ship speed, we do not see potential in changing out the propeller in operation. A similar point is made for the drive components such as the gearbox.
- G Energy: responsible for generating and storing energy, consisting of the power plant, energy sources, and energy storage. Here, the potential in a modular system is to change the power plant, for example when power demand changes based on the factory equipment. It is also to be ready for developments in power generation and energy carrier solutions, such as fuel cell technology, alternative fuels, or nuclear energy.
- H Accommodation: responsible for housing the crew, consisting of crew spaces such as cabins and mess room. Here we also do not see potential in modularisation, as the number of crew and their requirements is not foreseen to change significantly.
- I Bridge: responsible for navigation, communication, fish finding, and general monitoring and control, consisting of the equipment with these functions. Except for possibly upgrading navigation and communication hardware, we do not see a large benefit in modularising this system. Besides, any software upgrades are often done over-the-air nowadays.

Designing the trawler then comes down to defining which systems should be prepared for modularity, and which should rather be part of the platform. A mapping of the anticipated fishing missions for the vessel forms the basis for this decision. This also benefits handling the technical complexity of the system, by having a clear distinction between modular and integral systems. The configuration of the modules on board of the catch platform is then decided based on the specific fishing mission and product strategy relevant at that point in time.

3.2. Module interfaces

Components are, by definition, connected to other components by some physical interface. The availability of an interface in the intended location of a module determines if it is possible to place the module on board. In addition, the mating of the interfaces of interacting components is required to make the system work. A variety of interface types can be found on a trawler:

- Mechanical
 - Static, such as the fastening of processing equipment to the factory floor
 - Moving, such as the connection of the propeller shaft to the gearbox
- Material, such as the fish products
- Fluid and gas
 - Water, such as for rinsing or bleeding tanks
 - Refrigerant, such as supplied to the plate freezers
 - Hot air, such as to the fish meal plant
 - Compressed air, for some machines that use vacuum technology
- Electricity, possibly in various voltages and frequencies
- Information and control, such as a network cable for sensor data

3.3. Exchanging of modules

The main point of attention when introducing a modular solution is the exchange of modules between fishing trips. This operation must be simple and effective, as to minimise the loss of fishing days. An effective system for transferring modules should be designed, customised to the identified modules and their required interfaces.

An opening in the hull must be available to exchange the modules through. This must be placed such that there is access to the intended location of the module, and must be large enough such that all the possible modules fit through. To ensure watertightness and structural integrity of the ship, such an opening should be closed with a hatch when at sea.

There are various ways in which a hatch can be designed impacting the exchange of modules. A hatch in the deck means that a module must be lifted into the ship by crane and then moved to its intended place. The crane can be either the ship's own crane or a crane at the dock. A hatch in the side of the ship however means the module is moved only horizontally, given the hatch is located on the same deck as the module. The decision for what type of hatch to employ also depends on the facilities available at the prospected docking location.

An added benefit of having a hatch in the hull, is that major maintenance on components – even those not part of the modular solution – becomes less cumbersome. This might even be done on land during a fishing trip where the component is not required, saving further on time at the dock and minimising the potential loss of fishing days.

3.4. Impact on ship behaviour

Both the design changes required for exchanging modules and the exchanging of modules in operation will have an impact on the ship behaviour.

Modularity might be expected to imply larger ships from a design perspective, as the vessel is supposed to accommodate for every module variation. Larger ships in turn have a higher resistance, which increases propulsion power demand and thus fuel costs.

Depending on the size and type of module, the weight may have a significant impact. Adding weight will always work negatively for the stability of the vessel, especially when placed high up in the ship.

Additionally, weight components must be balanced as to minimise the roll and trimming moments, thus limiting the need for ballast. Furthermore, the dynamic behaviour of the vessel may be affected by the configuration of the modules. For example, adding tanks for liquid products could introduce additional dynamic loads through sloshing effects, which must be accounted for in the stability analysis.

The energy demand of the factory will impact the choice and design of the power plant. It is therefore key that the power plant can adapt to the factory's demand, by being part of the modular solution.

The addition of a hatch will have an impact on the overall ship strength. Additionally, the regulation for compartmentalisation and water tight sections must be approved. New guidelines might be required to assess the impacts of modularisation on the regulatory compliance.

4. An example: the modular factory

In recent years, more vessels in the Norwegian fleet have installed a shrimp line. The main reason for this is a reduction in whitefish quota, combined with a wish to keep the vessel running throughout the year (in order to keep the crew). An alternative would be to reduce the catch rate of whitefish, however this is not seen as profitable because of the good prices in high-season. Therefore, catching shrimp in the off-season is seen as an acceptable alternative to tying the vessel to the dock. This "mixed" fishing mission has become common throughout the oceangoing fleet. The fishing mission and product strategy is expressed as follows:

Fishing for whitefish 8–10 out of 10 trips. The catch is headed and gutted (HG), sorted by species, quality, and size, and frozen in blocks of 25 or 50 kilograms.

Fishing for shrimp 0–2 out of 10 trips. The catch is sorted by size and quality and frozen in blocks of 25 or 50 kilograms.

Bycatch – the catch of non-targeted species – is handled in the same way in both fishing missions. The amount and type of bycatch varies a lot by season, fishing area, and individual fishing trip. Therefore it is not elaborated on here.

The modular solution proposed in this example is to exchange the shrimp line for a residual raw material (RRM) line when in the appropriate season. The only modular components in this case are thus located on the factory deck, system C from the previous section. A sketch of the factory deck is shown in Figure 3..

Increased utilisation of the RRM from whitefish could be considered low-hanging fruit, as it is possible to prepare high-value raw materials from this on board. The oceangoing trawler fleet is lagging behind in this, only utilising around 41% as compared to nearly 100% for the coastal fleet. This is mainly due to older vessels in the fleet, which generally do not have space to store the RRM or do not have processes required to stabilise the RRM. Newer vessels do have ways to utilise the RRM as meal and oil, or as ensilage [16]. However, making space on board for this in addition to a shrimp line means the vessel needs to be significantly larger, causing a higher resistance, required power, and operating costs. Being able to exchange the shrimp line for a RRM line could increase the value creation on board while keeping the vessel the same size. Figure 4. shows the processing steps for the various products. The steps for shrimp are taken from [17], for whitefish from [18], and for RRM from [7].

4.1. Shrimp line

The shrimp line consists of a semi-automatic sorting station that grades the shrimp based on size. Afterwards, there is a manual control on quality and the removal of unwanted objects and animals. The shrimp are then kept in intermediate storage until a batch can be frozen in the plate freezers. The resulting product is industry shrimp (Norwegian: *industrireker*), which are stored in blocks on pallets until delivery on land.

An alternative is to boil the shrimp on board before freezing. This gives a higher value of the product and in some cases it can directly be sold on the consumer market. However, a boiler is required that takes space and energy. With the vessels already being limited on power, we focus on the simple case here where the shrimp are frozen raw.

Figure 3. Sketch of the proposed factory deck layout in shrimp configuration (above) and RRM configuration (below). Solid lined boxes indicate integral components, while dash lined boxes are the modular components. The icons indicate products produced in each area.

Figure 4. Processing steps for the various products. Dashed boxes indicate processing steps for which the components would be exchanged in the modular design. The icons indicate products produced in each step.

4.2. Residual raw material line

We estimate what components a RRM line should be composed of by identifying potential products that may be stored on board. The RRM of whitefish produced on a HG trawler consists of the head and viscera (liver, gonad, and guts).

The cod head may be exported whole if large enough. This has been common practice for a long time and can be assumed to apply to around one-third of the catch. For the rest of the RRM, several studies show that enzymatic hydrolysis can be used to produce high-quality protein hydrolysates (protein powder) for human consumption, for example from cod residuals [19, 20]. An alternative is use in animal feed, which requires a lower standard of material properties, for example with saithe viscera [21]. The hydrolysis process is done on land, with the trawlers providing the raw material. The advantage of this approach is that the onboard system remains relatively simple. Currently, it is not clear what amount of processing, if any, of the RRM should be done. While processes such as grinding or pressing reduces the size of the material and are thus beneficial for storage, this might have an influence on the possibilities in the hydrolysis process. Furthermore, the space and energy requirements of processing machines should be evaluated against the potential benefits. There are various ways to stabilise the material, where freezing and ensilage are the most common. As ensilage requires the addition of acid and storage in a tank, here we consider the option of freezing the material after sorting, using the same freezers as for the HG whitefish.

The residual raw material line could thus compose of a sorting station, potentially processing equipment, and a series of storage tanks. The tanks are used as extra intermediate storage of the various RRM components, such that the regular intermediate storage tanks can be reserved for whitefish. The RRM is finally frozen in blocks and stored on pallets, as with the other products.

4.3. Design changes

For this example, the matching of interfaces is surmountable. The fastening to the factory floor could be done using bolts for fast connection. The factory floor could incorporate mounting rails or guide tracks to allow for easy alignment and fastening of the modules. The input and output of material is handled by transport belt. A variety of belts exists, including those capable of going around corners. The most important is to match the height at which the belts enter components and adjust the speed to the components' capacity. Where an electricity connection is required, for the drive motors of transport belts or for potential processing equipment in the residual raw material line, a standardised plug should be used to ensure a quick and safe connection.

To allow for exchanging modules, a hatch must be available. All vessels already have a hatch through which the fish products are unloaded currently. A straightforward solution is therefore to also use this to exchange modules. This does require a 'route' from the location of the module to the hatch, that is not blocked by integral components. Again, the use of mounting rails could streamline movement through the ship. It may also prove useful to match the module dimensions to the product storage units (pallets), as this means less changes to the handling systems on land are required; the same fork trucks could be used to move both module and products.

The impact on ship behaviour is also limited in this case. The components of the shrimp and RRM line are foreseen to be of a similar weight, such that there is no issue with stability. There is probably no significant difference in power requirement for these components, so there is no need for changing the power plant. Accommodating for a route for moving the module out of the vessel might require more openings in the internal bulkheads in the vessel though, which could have an impact on the strength or water tight sections. As any structural changes must be approved by classification societies, early engagement with these regulatory bodies helps with the implementation of a modular system.

5. Discussion

In this work, we summarised the challenges to oceangoing trawler design and presented a possible way to handle these challenges by introducing the idea of a modular trawler design. The main points of attention when designing for modularity were touched upon. These are system identification, the matching

of component interfaces, facilitating for exchanging the modules, and identifying the impact on the ship behaviour.

The main contribution presented here is to apply the ship design for modularity strategy to a trawler design, something which has not been done before. This aligns with a broader trend in ship design where handling uncertainty characterises the design process.

We do however realise that the presented study is not complete. Quantified estimations of the operational benefits and implementation costs, as well as the impact of the modular system on ship behaviour are identified as further work. These estimations will then be used as the basis for an optimisation model that gives insight on the optimal module configuration given a select number of fishing missions. For designing the platform, a variety of requirements and constraints are identified: from realistic length–width ratios and the vessel’s stability to the workability on board, the platform has to offer a viable alternative to the current practice. The results of this future work will be quantitatively assessed through one or multiple performance indicators, an obvious possibility being the forecasted return on investment.

In addition, there are some industrial challenges to be solved. Standardisation of onboard components reduces the competitive position a supplier may have from providing a unique product. This concern could be addressed through developing interface standards, similar to those in other industries. There must be a given incentive for suppliers to participate in the development of such standards for this to succeed.

One can also argue that the example presented in the previous section is not very ambitious, following from the limited need for design changes that were found. This simple example was chosen because of the novelty of applying modular design to the trawler, as well as the recent trend towards better utilisation of residual raw material. Furthermore, interviews with the local industry in western Norway were held in other, ongoing work in the research project [22]. These resulted in new empirical evidence of conventions in the design process that mean the industry faces struggles when developing new solutions. This industry is generally risk-averse, and changes are met with scepticism. Therefore, it makes sense to start with something simple.

Other cases that could be used to assess a modular solution, where part of the factory is switched out for another, could be adding extra whitefish equipment, adding equipment for redfish and flatfish, or adding equipment for crab fishing. Furthermore, a case on a fully modular factory could be interesting, where it is possible to step away from whitefish completely. Finally, other systems than the factory should be included in the assessment. The energy system comes to mind here first, where flexible power generation could be a benefit of the modular solution. It is also possible to expand the way of thinking presented in this work to other vessel types, given that the requirements to the vessel that is considered are expected to change over the lifetime.

To conclude, the current work opens the discussion into thinking of the trawler as a catch platform. It is clear that a change from the current practice is required to secure the continued sustainable exploitation of fish stocks. It is expected that the whitefish quota will continue to sink or remain at a low level the coming years, such that it could be increasingly important to look at harvesting other species. Shrimp in the Barents Sea stands out as a species undergoing a relatively low fishing pressure currently, which could increase if the economic situation calls for it [23].

Acknowledgements

This work was supported by the FISH 4.0 research project, funded by the Research Council of Norway grant number 331829.

References

- [1] Kai Levander. *System Based Ship Design*. NTNU Marine Technology, 2012.
- [2] Fiskeridirektoratet. Økonomiske og biologiske nøkkeltal frå dei norske fiskeria 2024 / Economic and biological figures from the Norwegian fisheries 2024. Technical report, Fiskeridirektoratet, February 2025.
- [3] Dag Standal and Frank Asche. Hesitant reforms: The Norwegian approach towards ITQ’s. *Marine Policy*, 88:58–63, February 2018.
- [4] Rachel Tiller. En fiskehistorie som går både opp og ned. *Fiskeribladet*, April 2025.

- [5] Jose Jorge Garcia Agis, Per Olaf Brett, Ali Ebrahimi, and André Keane. Quantifying the effects of uncertainty in vessel design performance – a case study on factory stern trawlers. In *Proceedings of the 13th International Marine Design Conference*, Helsinki, Finland, 2018.
- [6] Veronica Hjellnes, Turid Rustad, and Eva Falch. The value chain of the white fish industry in Norway: History, current status and possibilities for improvement – A review. *Regional Studies in Marine Science*, 36:101293, April 2020.
- [7] Per Solibakke. Implications of Improving Resource Efficiency When Utilizing Residual Raw Material on Trawlers Producing Head and Gutted Fish. In *IFIP Advances in Information and Communication Technology*, pages 200–214, Trondheim, Norway, 2023. Springer Nature Switzerland.
- [8] Norbert H. Doerry. Institutionalizing Modular Adaptable Ship Technologies. *Journal of Ship Production and Design*, 30(3):126–141, August 2014.
- [9] Stein Ove Erikstad. Design for Modularity. In Apostolos Papanikolaou, editor, *A Holistic Approach to Ship Design*, volume 1. Springer Cham, 1 edition, 2019.
- [10] Karl Ulrich. The role of product architecture in the manufacturing firm. *Research Policy*, 24(3):419–440, May 1995.
- [11] F Salvador, C Forza, and M Rungtusanatham. Modularity, product variety, production volume, and component sourcing: theorizing beyond generic prescriptions. *Journal of Operations Management*, 20(5):549–575, September 2002.
- [12] Minjoo Choi, Stein Ove Erikstad, and Hyun Chung. Operation platform design for modular adaptable ships: Towards the configure-to-order strategy. *Ocean Engineering*, 163:85–93, September 2018.
- [13] James V. Jolliff. Modular Ship Design Concepts. *Naval Engineers Journal*, 86(5):11–32, October 1974.
- [14] Joaquin Sapien. The Inside Story of How the Navy Spent Billions on the "Little Crappy Ship". *ProPublica*, September 2023.
- [15] Stefan Pfeifer, Tobias Seidenberg, Christoph Jürgehake, Harald Anacker, and Roman Dumitrescu. Towards a modular product architecture for electric ferries using Model-Based Systems Engineering. In *Procedia Manufacturing*, volume 52, pages 228–233, 2020.
- [16] Magnus Myhre, Roger Richardsen, Ragnar Nystøyl, and Gunn Strandheim. Analyse marint restråstoff 2023. Technical Report 2024:00583, SINTEF Ocean, June 2024.
- [17] Cecilie Salomonsen and Leif Grimsmo. Ombordhåndtering av industrireker – forslag til teknologiske løsninger. Technical report, SINTEF Fiskeri og havbruk, August 2013.
- [18] Kristina Norne Widell, Guro Møen Tveit, Cecilia Gabriell, Emily Cowan, Leif Grimsmo, and Erik S. Svendsen. Equipment and systems onboard fishing vessels. Technical Report 2021:00739, SINTEF Ocean, September 2021.
- [19] Jannicke Fugledal Remme, Guro Møen Tveit, Morten Bondø, Rasa Slizyte, Aðalheiður Ólafsdóttir, Rósa Jónsdóttir, Margrét Geirsdóttir, and Ana Karina Carvajal. Valorisation of Frozen Cod (*Gadus morhua*) Heads, Captured by Trawl and Longline by the Oceanic Fleet, by Enzymatic Hydrolysis. *Journal of Aquatic Food Product Technology*, 31(5):483–495, May 2022.
- [20] Dimitra Marinou, Charlotte Jacobsen, Davide Odelli, Krystalia Sarigiannidou, and Ann-Dorit Moltke Sørensen. Production of Protein Hydrolysates from Cod Backbone Using Selected Enzymes: Evaluation of Antioxidative and Antimicrobial Activities of Hydrolysates. *Marine Drugs*, 23(3):125, March 2025.
- [21] Line Skontorp Meidell, Rasa Slizyte, Revilija Mozuraityte, Ana Karina Carvajal, Turid Rustad, and Eva Falch. Valorization of Saithe (*Pollachius virens*) Residuals into Protein Hydrolysates—Silaging as Preservation Technology. *Foods*, 13(13):2133, July 2024.
- [22] Jesper van der Meij, Julia V. Bondeli, Lars Erik Nygård, Stian Skjong, and Karl Henning Halse. Drivers and barriers of technological innovation in the Norwegian bottom trawler fleet, 1960s–2025. Submitted to the International Journal of Maritime History (IJMH), June 2025.
- [23] Fabian Zimmermann, Hanna E. H. Danielsen, Johanna B. Marcussen, John T. Trochta, Georgina Vickery, Siri A. Olsen, Erik Berg, Aleksei Stesko, and Sergei Bakanov. Assessment report for northern shrimp (*Pandalus borealis*) in the Barents Sea (ICES Subareas 1 and 2). Technical report, Institute of Marine Research and Polar branch of the FSBSI "VINRO", November 2024.